

Evaluation of Online Booking System Reviews: Greek Tourists' perspective in Booking Behavior Evaluation Explored via Data Mining Techniques during Economic Recession

**Ioanna Giannoukou¹, Constantinos Halkiopoulos¹, Hera Antonopoulou¹, Evgenia Gkintoni²,
Panagiotis Togias¹, Gerasimos Panas³**

¹*Dept. of Business Administration, Technological Educational Institute of Western Greece, Greece*

²*Dept. of Psychology, University of Crete, Greece*

³*Dept. of Digital Media and Communication, Technological Educational Institute of Ionian Islands, Greece*

Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to illuminate the perspective that tourists and particularly Greeks demonstrate as far as their booking behavior concerned travel reviews during the period of economic recession. Especially online travel reviews written by consumers are ever more available and used to inform travel-related decisions.

The present research concentrated on the web platforms of intermediary firms and agencies that constitute the e-tourism sector. These are organizations that facilitate communication and transactions between the primary providers of travel and accommodation services (e.g. airlines, hotels, car hire firms), and potential consumers of those services. Blogs, online reviews (ORs), and social networking platforms are enabling travelers to share information, opinions, and knowledge about all kinds of goods and services in e-Tourism. Specifically, online reviews (ORs) can be considered as electronic versions of traditional WOM (e-WOM) and consist of comments published by travelers.

For the data collection, three self-report questionnaires were administered: a) E-WOM and Accommodation Scale (E-WOM), b) Emotion-Based Decision-Making Scale (EBDMS,) c) Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire (TEIQue) clarifying four factors of emotional state; well-being, self-control, emotionality and sociability.

There were being created their electronic versions through Google Forms service and posted through the website "<http://www.cicos.gr/iccmi2017/obsr>". Then the collected data were selected for analysis, with relevant transformations in order to have a suitable form for the implementation of the respective machine learning algorithms included in the software package R. The methodology, that was adopted, consists of two concrete phases. During the first phase, questionnaires were created and submitted. During the second phase, the data set were collected, preprocessed and analyzed based on Data Mining techniques evaluating the results. More specifically, classification algorithms were utilized so as to manage to describe hidden patterns. Also, the parameters of the algorithms were set, depending on the application cases, and the results were correlated with the demographic characteristics of the respondents, in order to evaluate and assess the significance of exported rules / conclusions.

Keywords: *Booking Behavior, Data Mining, Economic Recession, e-Tourism, R*

1. INTRODUCTION

Finding on-line information on travel destinations is one of the most popular processes from which tourists are increasingly benefiting. A growing use of online reports about travel destinations and their planning has been observed in recent years. For this reason an e-WOM (electronic word of mouth) can have a significant influence on the decisions related to the movements of the tourists that have been implemented. Relevant e-Marketer surveys indicate that the use of travel critics has proven to be a beneficial process for planning a trip (e.g. booking a place of residence). In view of the above, the present research attempts to investigate whether the online reviews influence the behavior of the tourist-traveler in planning his journey and that the traveler's own personality, and in particular aspects of his emotional intelligence, play a key role by mediating in decisions-making to choose the appropriate travel destination.

1.1. Use of Word of Mouth in Travel Planning

Word of mouth (WOM) communication refers to interpersonal communication among consumers concerning their personal experiences with a firm or a product. Previous studies illustrate the significance of WOM for consumers' purchase decisions especially within a service context. Because service products are intangible and cannot be easily described, consumers tend to rely on word of mouth from an experienced source to lower perceived risk and uncertainty. Word-of-mouth information search is greater in circumstances when a consumer is unfamiliar with a service provider, which is often the case for travel-related decisions. WOM has long been recognized as one of the important external information sources for travel planning. As the use of the Internet for travel planning becomes ever more prevalent, travel decision making processes are expected to become increasingly influenced by e-WOM.

Consumer reviews and ratings are the most accessible and prevalent form of e-WOM. Consumer reviews serve two distinct roles: 1) they provide information about products and services; and, 2) they serve as recommendations. Consumer reviews are perceived as particularly influential because they are written from a consumer's perspective and, thus, provide an opportunity for indirect experience. They are also perceived as more credible than information provided by marketers. Online consumer reviews appear to play an increasing role in consumer decision making processes. Importantly, almost half of those whose purchasing decision was influenced by consumer reviews said that consumers' opinions actually caused them to change their mind about what they purchased. Clearly, online consumer-generated information is taking on an important role in online travelers' decision making.

1.2. Emotional Based Decision Making Framework

Most theories of human reasoning and decision-making fall between two different positions. The first one argues that we make decisions in a way similar to that of solving problems in formal logic. According to this view, when faced with a problem, we form a list of all different options and their possible outcomes, and then we use logic in its best sense to perform a cost/benefit analysis that will provide us with the best possible choice. The second view considers reasoning and decision-making to be associative. That is, when confronted with a situation that requires a decision, we compare it to similar situations that have been encountered in the past, and tend to act accordingly. Emotion-Based Decision Making that models important aspects of emotional processing, and integrates these with other models of perception, motivation, behavior, and motor control. A particular emphasis is placed on using some of the mechanisms of emotions as building blocks for the acquisition of emotional memories that serve as biasing signals during the process of making decisions and selecting actions such as the choice of a traveling destination via booking services.

1.3. Emotional Intelligence of Travelers

Emotional intelligence, a type of social and personal intelligence, is important in managing interpersonal relationships and interactions, especially in the business sphere. Businesses that involve frequent customer contact and interaction, such as those in the field of tourism, can benefit from the application of multiple intelligences. The notion of emotional intelligence its applications to business is a vital theme in order to suggest an application to tourism, a sector based largely on the interaction between people. Emotional intelligence can be an effective tool and a benefit to tourist services, to reflection the tour operator's role as cultural mediator between tourists and host community, and to explore how emotional intelligence can help in this tourist/host relationship.

1.4. E-WOM and Accommodation Scale (E-WOM)

An online questionnaire was created using the E-WOM Accommodation Scale and was sent to the study sample by email and social networks. The questionnaire was primarily composed of closed-ended questions measured using a 7-point Likert-type scale. The sample was selected along purposive lines with a focus on identifying travelers who had recently read ORs when searching for information on accommodations while planning their holidays. This scale is analyzed in the following dimensions:

- *Information timeliness* refers to information that is up to date, current, and represents the state of the art of a product/service. In comparison to traditional WOM, ORs are available 24 hours a day. The most recent ORs are displayed first on COPs, so consumers can easily access the latest reviews published on specific accommodations.
- *Information understandability* refers to readability, interpretability, and ease of understanding, as well as language, semantic, and lexical expressions used by reviewers.
- *Information relevance* refers to the extent to which a review is applicable and helpful for a task at hand depends on different customer needs in specific situations ORs are relevant if they provide the kind of information a customer is looking for.
- *Information accuracy* is defined as the correctness in the mapping of stored information to the appropriate state in the real world that the information represents. The accuracy of information depends on travelers' perceptions that information is accurate, correct, believable, and credible.
- *Value-added information* is the extent to which information is beneficial and provides advantages from their use. ORs may empower a traveler's capacity to make informed decisions by providing information that is generally not easy to access through traditional marketing communications.
- *Information completeness* is defined as the extent to which information is of sufficient breadth, depth, and scope for the task at hand. Accordingly, a customer may judge a review as complete based on the degree to which information from ORs is comprehensive and exhaustive for booking accommodation.
- *Information quantity* is the extent to which the quantity or volume of available data is appropriate for a specific task Information quantity represents the number of ORs per accommodation; it is a peripheral cue to information processing since it is a short cut that consumers may use to make a decision.
- *Product Ranking* refers to a typology of categorical or numerical information based on travelers' overall (average) evaluation of accommodations in a destination. The ranking or numbers of stars represents the average customer's evaluation of accommodation and summarizes the proportion of positive, neutral, and negative reviews.

Figure 30: E-WOM Research Model

1.5. Emotion-Based Decision-Making Scale (EBDMS)

The Emotion-Based Decision-Making Scale (EBDMS) attempts to measure a person's tendency to rely upon emotions and "gut reactions" in making decisions. It has 10 items that use a 5-point Likert response scale. Five items are reverse-coded.

1.6. Trait Emotional Intelligence (EI)

For recording, tracing and evaluation concerning the emotional intelligence was used the standardized scale Trait

Image 1

Emotional Intelligence (TEIQue) which examines the Trait model of EI as proposed by K.V. Petrides. The Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire is a self-report questionnaire that has been developed to cover the trait EI sampling domain comprehensively. Questionnaire measures of EI have been proliferating over the past few years, and it is important to mention three advantages of the TEIQue over them to justify the focus of this research. First, the TEIQue is based on a psychological theory that integrates the construct into mainstream models of differential psychology. Second, the TEIQue provides comprehensive coverage of the 15 facets of the trait EI sampling domain. Several independent studies have demonstrated the ability of the TEIQue to predict criteria (outcomes) significantly better than other questionnaires. Third, the full TEIQue has excellent psychometric properties. Finally, the TEIQue has been used in numerous studies wherein the assessment of affective aspects of personality was required. These include research in the areas of neuroscience, relationship satisfaction, psychopathology, addictions, reaction time, general health, and behavioral genetics. The TEIQue provides an operationalization for the model of Petrides and colleagues that conceptualizes EI in terms of personality. The test encompasses 15 subscales organized under four factors:

- **Well being:** The Well-being factor comprises three different traits: Happiness, Optimism and Self-esteem. They measure how people judge their general level of life satisfaction.
- **Self control:** The Self-control factor describes how far people think they can control their impulses or are controlled by them. It comprises three different traits: Impulse Control, Stress Management and Emotional Regulation.
- **Emotionality:** The Emotionality factor comprises four different traits: Empathy, Emotion Perception, Emotion Expression and Relationships. Together they indicate how aware you may be of your own emotions and feelings, as well as those of other people.
- **Sociability:** The Sociability factor describes how comfortable people feel in different social contexts, from parties and social gatherings to formal business meetings.

2. METHODOLOGY

In this paper were applied Machine Learning and Data Mining methods in order to evaluate the booking behavior of Greek tourists using Emotion-Based Decision-Making Scale (EBDMS), the E-WOM and Accommodation Scale (E-WOM) and Emotional Intelligence Quotient (TEIQue) The methodology, that was adopted, consists of three concrete phases. During the first phase electronic questionnaires were created and posted through the website <http://www.cicos.gr>. Subsequently, data were collected and preprocessed from the questionnaires. The data set for analysis was consisted of demographics elements of responders, such as the gender, the birth-place, the place of present residence, educational background of both the respondents and their parents, professional occupation of parents and also of subscales of the CEAS, EQ, BEES, EPQ and TEIQue tests. During the third phase, the data set was analyzed based on Data Mining techniques and evaluate the results. More specifically, we utilized classification algorithms so as to manage to describe the hidden patterns underlying in the data. Decision trees are a powerful way in order to represent and facilitate statements analysis (psychological) principally, comprising successive decisions and variable results in a designated period.

2.1. Booking Behavior personal traits of Greek tourists during economic recession

Global financial community, it has been entered in a new and unknown economic phase. The huge crisis of the financial system, which has been arises in the developed countries results a risk of insolvency and has led to unstable economies and create millions of unemployed worldwide. Today, national economies are closely dependable each other. In addition, commercial and financial information is moving at breakneck speed through the Internet and mobile networks. It is true that unfavorable economic circumstances have a repercussion in the sector of travel industry which there is a need to be adjusted in an economic environment full of uncertainty, in order to address even the most demanding and needs of travelers. A useful element that travels industry, it is necessary to take into account is the different personality traits of travelers that interfere with their booking behavior and determine their decision-making towards their choice when they have to select a travel destination.

As far as the repercussion of personality traits in booking behavior, recent advances in personality psychology can help us predict tourist motivation. Traits are defined as enduring and stable patterns of behavior, attitudes, emotions, that vary between individuals. Traditionally, researchers were interested in understanding how individuals differ, and so they put a great deal of effort into discovering how to measure, map, and define personality traits. An effort

was made through trait theory in order to define personality traits. Trait theory suggests that personality is made up of a set of quantitative measurable characteristics or units known as traits. Traits are pre-dispositional attribute and are relatively stable. Every personality has a unique combination of traits and given its stability, people with a given combination of traits can be expected to behave consistently across situations and over time. The development of trait theory is attributed to the pioneering works of psychologists such as, Gordon Allport, Henry Odbert Raymond Cattell and Hans Eysenck.

2.2. Data Mining Techniques

Data Mining is an emerging knowledge discovery process of extracting previously unknown, actionable information from very large scientific and commercial databases. It is imposed by the explosive growth of such databases. Usually, a data mining process extracts rules by processing high dimensional categorical and/or numerical data. Classification, clustering and association are the most well known data mining tasks. Classification is one of the most popular data mining tasks. Classification aims at extracting knowledge which can be used to classify data into predefined classes, described by a set of attributes. The extracted knowledge can be represented using various schemas.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Association Rule Learning

Association rule learning is a rule-based machine learning method for discovering interesting relations between variables in large databases. It is intended to identify strong rules discovered in databases using some measures of interestingness. They are usually required to satisfy a user-specified minimum support and a user-specified minimum confidence at the same time. Association rule generation is usually split up into two separate steps:

- vii. A minimum support threshold is applied to find all frequent itemsets in a database.
- viii. A minimum confidence constraint is applied to these frequent itemsets in order to form rules.
- ix. While the second step is straightforward, the first step needs more attention.

Three most widely used measures ⁸for selecting interesting rules are:

Support

Support is an indication of how frequently the itemset appears in the dataset.

Confidence

Confidence is an indication of how often the rule has been found to be true.

Lift

Is the ratio of the observed support to that expected if X and Y were independent.

Apriori is an algorithm for frequent item set mining and association rule learning over transactional databases. It proceeds by identifying the frequent individual items in the database and extending them to larger and larger item sets as long as those item sets appear sufficiently often in the database. The frequent item sets determined by Apriori can be used to determine association rules which highlight general trends in the database.

3.2. Visualizing Extracted Rules

⁸Every rule is composed by two different sets of items, also known as itemsets, X and Y, where X is called antecedent or left-hand-side (LHS) and Y consequent or right-hand-side (RHS).

Visualization has a long history of making large data sets better accessible using techniques like selecting and zooming. In this paper we use the R-extension package “arulesViz” which implements several known and novel visualization techniques to explore association rules. Below, we represent the extracted rules in a variety of ways with different techniques.

Graph-based visualization

Graph-based visualization offers a very clear representation of rules but they tend to easily become cluttered and thus are only viable for very small sets of rules

Grouped Matrix Visualization

Antecedents (columns) in the matrix are grouped using clustering. Groups are represented as balloons in the matrix.

Parallel coordinates visualization

Parallel coordinates plots are designed to visualize multidimensional data where each dimension is displayed separately on the x-axis and the y-axis is shared. Each data point is represented by a line connecting the values for each dimension

Apriori rules

Specifically of our use we altered the Support and Confidence values to 40% and 90% respectively

A sample of the extracted rules (Top 10)

lhs	rhs	support	confidence	lift
1 {EI_self_control=LOW, EWOM_Value.added.information.=LOW, EWOM_Product.Ranking.=LOW}	=> {EI_sociability=LOW}	0.4000000	1.0000000	2.058824

```

47 {EI_sociability=LOW,
    EWOM_Product.Ranking.=LOW}      => {EWOM_Value.added.information.=LOW}  0.4571429 1.0000000 1.521739
48 {EI_sociability=LOW,
    EWOM_Information.quantity.=LOW}   => {EWOM_Product.Ranking.=LOW}          0.4285714 1.0000000 1.521739
96 {EBDSMS_logic=LOW,
    EWOM_Information.accuracy.=LOW}   => {EI_self_control=LOW}                0.4285714 0.9375000 1.426630
105 {Sex=Female,
    X.10.Use.of.social.media.during.your.trip.=Yes,
    EWOM_Information.accuracy.=LOW}   => {EWOM_Value.added.information.=LOW}  0.4000000 0.9333333 1.420290
120 {EBDSMS_logic=LOW,
    EWOM_Information.understandability.=LOW} => {EWOM_Information.quantity.=LOW}    0.4285714 0.9375000 1.367188
127 {EI_sociability=LOW,
    EWOM_Information.relevance.=LOW}  => {EWOM_Information.understandability.=LOW} 0.4285714 1.0000000 1.346154
128 {EBDSMS_emotion=LOW,
    EWOM_Value.added.information.=LOW} => {EWOM_Information.understandability.=LOW} 0.4857143 1.0000000 1.346154
107 {EWOM_Information.completeness.=HIGH} => {EWOM_Information.timeliness=HIGH}    0.4000000 1.0000000 1.400000
6 {EBDSMS_emotion=LOW,
    EWOM_Value.added.information.=LOW} => {EWOM_Information.completeness.=LOW}  0.4857143 1.0000000 1.666667

```

3.3. Principal Component Analysis

Principal component analysis (PCA) is a statistical procedure that uses an orthogonal transformation to convert a set of observations of possibly correlated variables into a set of values of linearly uncorrelated variables called principal components (or sometimes, principal modes of variation). The number of principal components is less than or equal to the smaller of the number of original variables or the number of observations. This transformation is defined in such a way that the first principal component has the largest possible variance (that is, accounts for as much of the variability in the data as possible), and each succeeding component in turn has the highest variance possible under the constraint that it is orthogonal to the preceding components. PCA is sensitive to the relative scaling of the original variables.

Standard deviations:

1.2275791 1.0225014 0.6689847

Rotation:

	PC1	PC2	PC3
EBDSMS_logic	-0.4508378	0.75086036	0.4826531
EBDSMS_emotion	0.7220868	-0.01107247	0.6917139
EI_emotionality	0.5247247	0.66036817	-0.5371944

Importance of components:

	PC1	PC2	PC3
Standard deviation	1.2276	1.0225	0.6690
Proportion of Variance	0.5023	0.3485	0.1492
Cumulative Proportion	0.5023	0.8508	1.0000

4. CONCLUSION

Our results show that travelers are not influenced by the completeness of information. Most travelers appear to only search for information that satisfies their particular needs. Therefore, they are not interested in knowing everything about specific accommodations and may not read all the content in a review; rather they are only interested in the kind of information that satisfies their information needs.

References

- [81] Cooper, A., Petrides, K.V. (2010). A Psychometric Analysis of the Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire-Short Form (TEIQue-SF) Using Item Response Theory. *Journal of Personality Assessment*, 92 (5), 449-457.
- [82] Eysenck H.J, (1950), Criterion analysis – an application of the hypothetic – deductive method in factor analysis, *Psychol. Rev.* 1950, 57, p. 38 – 53.
- [83] Eysenck, H.J. & Eysenck, S.B.G, (1968). A factorial study of Psychotism as a dimension of personality. *Cultivariate Behaviour Research*, Special Issue.
- [84] Gkintoni, E., Halkiopoulos, C., Antonopoulou, H., Togiias, P., Mitropoulos, A., “Emotional Intelligence in Social Network Consumers”, *International Conference on Contemporary Marketing Issues*, 22-24 June 2016, Heraklion, Greece
- [85] Gkintoni, E., Halkiopoulos, C., Antzoulatos, G., Giannopoulou, G., "Emotional Intelligence Evaluation in Greek Adolescents: A Data Mining Approach", *International Conference on Adolescent Medicine and Child Psychology*, September 28-30, 2015, Houston, USA, [Online] Available from: <http://www.cicos.gr/eiega/>, [Accessed: 30th June 2015].
- [86] Mikolajczak, Luminet; Leroy; Roy (2007). "Psychometric Properties of the Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire: Factor Structure, Reliability, Construct, and Incremental Validity in a French-Speaking Population". *Journal of Personality Assessment*, 88 (3): 338–353.
- [87] Petrides, K. V. & Furnham, A. (2006). The role of trait emotional intelligence in a gender-specific model of organizational variables. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 36, 552-569.
- [88] Petrides, K.V.; Furnham, A. (2003). "Trait emotional intelligence: behavioral validation in two studies of emotion recognition and reactivity to mood induction". *European Journal of Personality*, 17: 39–75.
- [89] Mikolajczak, Luminet; Leroy; Roy (2007). Psychometric Properties of the Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire: Factor Structure, Reliability, Construct, and Incremental Validity in a French-Speaking Population. *Journal of Personality Assessment*, 88 (3): 338–353.
- [90] Oded Maimon and Lior Rokach (Editors), “Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery Handbook”, 2nd ed., Springer, 2010.
- [91] Pang-Ning Tan, Michael Steinbach and Vipin Kumar, “Introduction to Data Mining”, Addison-Wesley, 2006.
- [92] R Development Core Team (2008). R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. ISBN 3-900051-07-0, URL <http://www.R-project.org>.

- [93] Togias, P., Margaritis, S., Papaioannou, B., Mortoglou, A., Gkintoni, E., Halkiopoulos, C., Antzoulatos, G., "Evaluation of Emotional Intelligence Quotient with the Use of Machine Learning Methods", *4th Panhellenic Interdisciplinary Conference "Mental Health, Technology and Telematic Applications"*, March 2015, Athens. [Online] Available from: <http://www.cicos>.
- [94] Udo-Imeh, P., Awara, N., Essien, E. (2015). Personality and Consumer Behaviour: A Review. *European Journal of Business and Management*: 7 (18). ISSN 2222-2839 Available Online: www.iiste.org: ISSN 2222-1905
- [95] Mehrabian, A. (1996). *Manual for the Balanced Emotional Empathy Scale (BEES)*. (Available from Albert Mehrabian, 1130 Alta Mesa Road, Monterey, CA, USA 93940).
- [96] Albiero, P., Matricardi, G., Speltri, D., Toso, D. (2009). The assessment of empathy in adolescence: A contribution to the Italian validation of the "Basic Empathy Scale". *Journal of Adolescence* 32: 393-408.
- [97] Agres, Stuart J. Julie A. Edell and Tony M. Dubitsky (1990), *Emotion in Advertising: Theoretical and Practical Explorations*, 18, 383-401.
- [98] Kidwell, Blair, & Richard McFarland (2005), "Emotional calibration on consumer decision making: Ability and confidence as predictors of performance," Paper presented at The 2005 International Research Seminar in Consumer Behavior, La Londe les Maures, France.
- [99] Baron-Cohen, S. and Wheelwright, S. (2004) The Empathy Quotient: An Investigation of Adults with Asperger Syndrome or High Functioning Autism, and Normal Sex Differences. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 34, 163-175. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1023/B:JADD.0000022607.19833.00>